

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B UPDATED SYNERGIES STRATEGY

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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PLANET4B

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Key deliverable information

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
CAC	The Climate Academy
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DEAR	EU's programme for Development Education and Awareness Raising
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
GD	GoodIssue nonprofit Ltd.
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
IPBES	Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIFE	EU's programme for the environment and climate action
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
RU	Radboud University
TCBPI database	Transformative change for biodiversity projects and initiatives database
TEHRA	The Environment and Human Rights Academy
UNEP-WCMC	United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIPI	University of Pisa
WP	Work Package

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Executive summary

- This Updated Synergies Strategy (D5.6) is informed by a review of the previous D5.5 Synergies Strategy that was produced in Month 6 of the PLANET4B project.
- A seven-step process was successfully implemented for identifying, coordinating and delivering collaborative activities with projects and initiatives that share synergies with PLANET4B.
- During implementation of the D5.5 Synergies Strategy, PLANET4B established contact with approximately 60 projects and initiatives and conducted 23 joint activities with other EU-funded and non-EU funded projects, as well as co-leading the “Values, Norms and Justice Working Group”.
- PLANET4B’s collaborative efforts with other projects have strengthened the project’s visibility, expanded the uptake, and enhanced collective messages on biodiversity, behaviour change, plural values, intersectionality and social inclusion. It has also paved the way for sustained impact beyond the lifetime of the PLANET4B project.
- Continued involvement of PLANET4B’s partners in knowledge networks, future events and follow-on projects will help to further ensure the long-term legacy and wider uptake of PLANET4B’s research and outputs.

1 Introduction

PLANET4B is a Horizon Europe project, under the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster, that seeks to understand intersectionality, behaviour and the motivations around biodiversity prioritisation in decision-making through transdisciplinary research. PLANET4B’s research draws on a broad range of theoretical concepts that cut across many academic disciplines, including sociology, systems science, behavioural science, conservation science, political science, and many more. PLANET4B has produced knowledge, research and guidance products that have high relevance for a range of target audiences, including policymakers, business actors, civil society and academia. On account of the far-reaching scope of PLANET4B’s research and its relevance for a range of audiences, PLANET4B shares synergies with a broad range of projects and initiatives in the wider research landscape. There are many benefits to establishing cooperation and collaboration with other research projects. In particular, it can facilitate knowledge-exchange and cross-project learning, reveal synergies and opportunities to communicate joint research messages, encourage the uptake of PLANET4B’s research into current and future research projects, and much more. The rationale for developing the D5.5 Synergies Strategy (Kaye, S. & Zolyomi, A., 2023) and the D5.6 Updated Synergies Strategy, is the knowledge that by building synergies with other research projects and initiatives, PLANET4B can maximise its reach and impact.

This Updated Synergies Strategy forms one of the deliverables (D5.6) of Task 5.3 *Mapping synergies and creating cooperation with existing initiatives and projects* led by UNEP-WCMC in the PLANET4B project. The purpose of this Updated Synergy Strategy (D5.6) is firstly to provide a review of progress in the implementation of the D5.5 Synergy Strategy, and secondly to expand on possibilities for further collaborations with projects and initiatives beyond the lifetime of the PLANET4B project.

1.1 Background

Collaboration between research projects is widely recognised as important for improving the quality, relevance and reach of research efforts. However, barriers can prevent projects from allocating time and resources to establishing collaborations with other projects. For example, projects are often bound by tight timelines, fixed objectives and limited resources. These constraints can make it difficult for project teams to allocate time and resources to collaborative activities that extend beyond the central objectives of the project. Further, differences in project design, scope, and disciplinary focus can pose challenges for aligning research activities, even when clear synergies exist between projects. Finally, practical barriers, such as identifying the most relevant projects within a complex landscape of research projects, establishing effective communication channels across diverse consortia and ensuring sustained engagement over time, can constrain collaboration between projects. As a result, opportunities to build synergies, jointly pursue common research aims, and amplify collective research messages are often missed. Recognising this limitation, the European Commission supports projects funded through the Horizon Europe research programme to build synergies and foster collaboration with other research projects. The present D5.5 Synergies Strategy was developed to proactively address these challenges and demonstrate how meaningful and constructive cooperation between projects can be achieved. In particular, this D5.5 Synergies Strategy and the D5.6 Updated Synergies Strategy aim to support the realisation of four key outcomes,

- **Knowledge sharing:** ensuring PLANET4B outputs are shared, used and built upon in other projects.
- **Knowledge co-production:** developing joint research and products in shared areas of interest.
- **Joint dissemination:** coordinating communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.
- **Future collaboration:** identifying actions that extend beyond project lifespans to sustain and amplify impact.

A first iteration of this Synergies Strategy (D5.5) was produced in Month 6 of the project. The purpose of the D5.5 Synergies Strategy was to map and record existing projects and initiatives that have synergistic complementarity with the PLANET4B project¹, in the form of a “Transformative Change for Biodiversity Projects and Initiatives database” (TCBPI database). The TCBPI database has been integral to the implementation of Task 5.3, serving as a living repository of information on other projects and initiatives that share synergies with PLANET4B. The second objective of the D5.5 Synergies Strategy was to outline a process and timeline for how collaboration with other projects and initiatives would take place. The D5.5 Synergies Strategy provided a roadmap for collaboration with other Horizon Europe projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity cCluster as well as other EU and non-EU funded projects and initiatives. The Strategy was also intended to serve as a guideline for the PLANET4B project partners, to clarify the plan for how PLANET4B would engage and collaborate with other projects, including their role in supporting the implementation of the Strategy. The D5.5 Synergies Strategy was also intended to be

¹ The D5.5 Synergies Strategy and D5.6 Updated Synergies Strategy defines “project” to mean an enterprise that has been funded and planned to achieve a particular aim. It defines “initiative” to take a broader meaning relating to schemes, campaigns, organisations and networks that are planned to achieve a particular aim and initiatives.

a call to action to other projects, to encourage other projects and initiatives to contact the PLANET4B project to propose their own ideas for joint project activities.

In line with its stated intention, the D5.5 Synergy Strategy has served as a living strategy throughout the PLANET4B project. In practice, this has involved ensuring an ongoing and iterative process of mapping other projects and initiatives, conducting and monitoring outreach and engagement with external projects, delivering joint activities with external projects, and updating the TCBPI database on an ongoing basis throughout the project.

With support from the European Commission, Horizon Europe-funded projects under the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster were encouraged to form working groups based on their complementarity with one another. A working group on “Values, Norms and Justice” (working group 3) was established and has been co-led by BioTraceS and PLANET4B since the conception of the PLANET4B project. To complement the D5.5 Synergies Strategy, in Month 9 of the PLANET4B project, the “Values, Norms and Justice Working Group” jointly developed a dedicated Deliverable 5.11 (Kaye et al., 2023) which sets out a joint work plan for how the working group would identify the synergies between the projects, coordinate activities and create frequent opportunities knowledge exchange and learning between projects.

2 Progress in implementing the seven-step process for identifying synergies and coordination collaboration with external projects and initiatives

In the D5.5 Synergies Strategy, a seven-step process was conceptualised to facilitate implementation of the Strategy. These steps consist of identifying and mapping similar projects and initiatives, assessing their synergistic complementarity, contacting the projects and initiatives, coordinating and implementing collaborative activities, communicating and disseminating, monitoring and reporting and setting plans for future collaboration (Figure 1). The D5.5 Synergies Strategy also outlined a timeline for implementing, monitoring and reviewing the Strategy between Month 9 and Month 30 of the project (Table 1).

Steps for identifying synergies and coordinating collaboration

Figure 1. Steps for identifying synergies and coordinating collaboration with external projects and initiatives. Source: D5.5 Synergies Strategy.

Table 1. Timeline and core activities of the synergies strategy. Source: D5.5 Synergies Strategy).

Timeframe	Activities
M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish synergies strategy • Begin reaching out to projects with the highest synergetic complementarity with PLANET4B until M12
Continuously (every six months from M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revise synergies strategy • Revise PLANET4B TCBPI database
M9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish Action Plan of Transformative Change Clustering (D5.11) • Develop an extended version of the PLANET4B TCBPI database
M12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stocktake of existing collaborations and revised plan and continue contacting external partners listed in PLANET4B TCBPI database until M30
M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publish updated synergies strategy (D5.6)

The following section provides an update on PLANET4B's progress on the seven-step process for implementing the Strategy according to the actions and timeframes set out in the D5.5 Synergies Strategy.

2.1 Identifying and mapping similar projects and initiatives

The D5.5 Synergies Strategy identified five broad types of projects and initiatives as a priority for exploring collaboration. These include:

1. International projects and initiatives beyond Europe

In the interest of ensuring PLANET4B project results feed into global policy processes, particular effort will be made by the PLANET4B consortium to collaborate with globally relevant initiatives, especially those linked to IPBES and IPCC assessments.

2. **European initiatives**

To build connection and strengthen impact at the EU level, opportunities for collaboration will be explored with other regional and European fora such as Eklipse, Biodiversa+, Oppla and the EC's Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity.

3. **Horizon Europe projects from the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster**

To strengthen collective research impact with other Horizon Europe projects under the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster, opportunities for joint actions will be mapped through cluster events and shared deliverables.

4. **Other Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects**

PLANET4B partners will also pursue collaborations with other Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects beyond the cluster, learning from earlier initiatives such as BioAgora and NetworkNature for the benefit of PLANET4B's research activities and supporting future Horizon Europe projects to build on PLANET4B results.

5. **Other relevant projects and initiatives**

PLANET4B will also seek to engage with other EU-funded programmes such as LIFE, DEAR, or Interreg mechanisms, to ensure PLANET4B contributes to and benefits from diverse biodiversity-related efforts.

The first step for developing and implementing the D5.5 Synergy Strategy involved creating the PLANET4B TCBPI database and mapping projects and initiatives that share synergies with PLANET4B. To create the initial TCBPI database, UNEP-WCMC reviewed the CORDIS project database and OpenAIRE Explore project database. The CORDIS project database was used for the mapping exercise because it provides the most comprehensive overview of results from EU projects from 1990 until now. Similarly, the OpenAIRE Explore online platform was used because it is an open dataset linking millions of projects to the grants and organisations associated with them. In order to improve the results of this mapping activity, a series of keyword search terms were used when reviewing the CORDIS and OpenAIRE databases. The criteria for selecting the keyword search terms was their thematic relevance to the PLANET4B's research objectives e.g. "biodiversity", "behavioural science", "intersectionality" and so on.

Between Month 9 and Month 36 of the project, UNEP-WCMC conducted ongoing mapping activities to identify new projects and initiatives that have synergistic complementarity with PLANET4B. The TCBPI database was continually updated with information on new projects and initiatives that share synergies with PLANET4B. Building on the first review of the CORDIS and OpenAIRE database in Month 9, ongoing searches were conducted of these databases using additional relevant keywords related to PLANET4B's research. Particular attention was given to identifying Horizon Europe projects that commenced after the first review was conducted. As well as reviewing the CORDIS and OpenAIRE databases, PLANET4B partners remained alert to information about other projects and initiatives that share synergies with PLANET4B through their social networks and passed on this information to UNEP-WCMC to include in the TCBPI database. The updated TCBPI database with the additional mapped projects and initiatives can be found in the [Annex](#).

2.2 Assessing synergistic complementarity

The TCBPI database has served as PLANET4B's go-to source of information for conducting further research into the synergistic complementarity of other projects and initiatives with PLANET4B. For each project or initiative mapped in the TCBPI database, a link to the relevant project or initiative was also provided. Visiting the website of the project or initiative was the first port of call for exploring information and materials that may provide insight on the potential synergies of the project with the PLANET4B project. This information was then recorded in an extended database for internal purposes, listing the specific topic of the project/initiative and envisioned type of co-operation.

2.3 Contacting and coordinating with synergistic projects and initiatives

To initiate contact with external projects, the names and contact details for the individual(s) leading the projects were obtained either via the projects' webpages or via other contacts who were already in touch with partners involved in the project. Using a standard template email that was developed by UNEP-WCMC, each project in the TCBPI database was systematically contacted. The template email used to initiate contact contained a brief description of the PLANET4B project and its objectives, a proposition to explore collaborative opportunities, suggestions for *types* of collaboration that PLANET4B is open to exploring, a link to the PLANET4B website and D5.5 Synergy Strategy, and a proposal for a follow-up meeting to jointly discuss ideas further.

Following initial contact with the mapped projects, a variety of responses were typically received, ranging from immediate confirmation of interest in exploring joint collaborations, information about upcoming project activities such as events and outputs that may present opportunities for collaboration in future, and suggestions for other projects and initiatives that may be more aligned to PLANET4B's research topics. In all instances, UNEP-WCMC maintained an up-to-date record of each correspondence in an internal spreadsheet. For those projects and initiatives for which no response was received, a further follow-up was sent CC'ing in other contacts where possible.

Once contact had been established, subsequent short meetings often took place to introduce the respective projects and discuss ideas for collaboration in more detail. These meetings were also used as an opportunity to agree how best to maintain communication and collaboration between PLANET4B and the external project (e.g. preferred means of communication and frequency of contact, etc). Once contact had been established with the external project or initiative and discussion had taken place as to the type of collaboration that we wanted to jointly pursue, implementation of the collaborative activity was either delegated to the relevant consortium partner with oversight from UNEP-WCMC, or directly implemented by UNEP-WCMC. Between Month 6 and Month 36, approximately 60 projects were contacted by UNEP-WCMC and other PLANET4B partners.

2.4 Communicating and disseminating and monitoring and reporting

Each time PLANET4B entered into collaboration with an external project or initiative, UNEP-WCMC and the WP5 lead (GD) worked with partners to define communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities suited to the form of cooperation, including:

- Coordinated social media campaigns highlighting joint work and outcomes
- Publicising shared events or workshops through available channels
- Engaging media organisations, including preparing joint press releases
- Publishing shared content online, such as articles or updates on relevant websites

Partners provided regular updates on their cooperation efforts during WP5 meetings, WP lead meetings and Steering Committee meetings. The Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation database developed by GoodIssue (GD) in the context of WP5 was also used by partners to record their collaboration activities with external projects. Progress in building links with EU projects was measured using a KPI that tracked the number of joint actions undertaken (target: 10). Throughout the project, during internal meetings, WP leads, Task leads and partners were reminded of the agreed process for identifying synergies and collaboration with other projects.

2.5 Setting future collaboration

The final step for implementing the D5.5 Synergies Strategy related to identifying strategies for future collaboration between PLANET4B and other projects, beyond the lifespan of the PLANET4B project. This final step is important for improving the sustainability of the project's results and the long-term impact of the project. Strategies for ensuring future collaborations can be found in [Section 4](#).

3 Result of collaborative activities with external projects and initiatives

The following table presents the results of PLANET4B's collaborative activities with external projects and initiatives between Month 9 and Month 36 of the project. The information in the table draws on information recorded in the TCBPI database, reporting from partners during partner meetings, and reporting by project partners on "joint actions with other EU projects" in the Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation Database developed by GD.

Table 2. Overview of collaborative activities conducted with external projects and initiatives.

Name of projects/initiative(s)	Type of collaboration	Description of the collaborative activity	Date of activity
Projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	First meeting of the "Transformative Change for Biodiversity" Cluster in Brussels to learn about each other's projects and identify synergies and collaborative opportunities.	17.03.2023

Shared Green Deal	Knowledge-sharing	Presented PLANET4B's research at the annual meeting of the Shared Green Deal project.	19.04.2023
MAIA	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	PLANET4B participated in the MAIA Thematic Group on Behavioural and Structural Change.	03.02.2024
Shared Green Deal	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research findings	Presented about PLANET4B at a webinar hosted by SHARED GREEN DEAL on the topic of "local actions for a shared green deal".	14.03.2024
Projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	Knowledge-sharing	Meeting of the "Values, Norms & Justice Working Group" of the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster. Held an "Exchange on theories of transformative change".	05.04.2024
WIDE-ARC project	Joint dissemination of research findings	Presented research from the textile extensive case study on the textile industry at a seminar on "Fairness and wellbeing in a Dematerialised Economy" alongside other research projects.	15.04.2024
Projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Held a "Narrative co-design workshop" with projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster.	06.06.2024
MAIA	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Second meeting of the Thematic Group on Behavioural and Structural Change.	19.07.2024
BIOTRAILS	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research findings	Presented PLANET4B's Transdisciplinary Diagnostic Framework and Reflexivity-Situatedness-Matrix at a webinar hosted by Ecosystem Services Partnership.	12.09.2024

European Forum on Urban Agriculture	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research findings	Presented research from the intensive case study on urban food gardens in Graz.	25.09.2024 – 26.09.2024
Projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Hosted a meeting of the “Values, Norms & Justice Working Group” of the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster.	04.10.2024
EU4GREEN	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Participated in a networking meeting with representatives from EU4GREEN.	30.10.2024
UNEP Global Environment Outlook 7 – working group on “social equity and behaviour change”	Knowledge sharing	Presented the research happening in PLANET4B to the co-chair of the working group on “social equity and behaviour change” for the UNEP Global Environment Outlook 7 Report.	16.01.2025
CircHive, BIOTRAILS, TC4BE, BIONEXT, SELINA, MOSAIC	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research messages	Presented PLANET4B’s work on systems mapping at the second joint webinar with sister projects on “Methodologies for mapping systems interactions”.	27.02.2025
Projects in the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research messages	Participated in a Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster meeting, hosted by the European Commission in Brussels. Took part in exercise to share and discuss findings from our respective projects.	03.06.2025
CLEVER, BIOTRAILS, BAMBOO, RAINFOREST BioTraCes, BIONEXT	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research findings	Attended the final CLEVER project meeting and presented PLANET4B’s research on intersectionality and inclusive approaches in transformative change.	04.06.2025 – 05.06.2025
A-Track	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Delivered a presentation on applying behaviour change methods in business contexts at a workshop hosted by the A-Track project for business actors.	10.06.2025

CircHive, BIOTRAILS, TC4BE, BIONEXT, SELINA, MOSAIC	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research messages	Presented PLANET4B's case studies during third joint webinar with sister projects on "Case studies as application examples".	26.06.2025
DAISY	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research messages	Two joint webinars with the DAISY project to share the results and tools developed in PLANET4B and identify joint policy messages.	11.06.2025, 29.07.2025
NetworkNature	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research messages	Presented PLANET4B's work during an exhibition hosted by NetworkNature at their final project event.	18.09.2025
BIOTRAILS, CircHive, BIONEXT	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research messages	Presented tools developed in PLANET4B during fourth joint webinar with sister projects on "Tools for Transformative Change for biodiversity".	23.09.2025
BIONEXT, BioAgora, Transpath, BioTraCes	Knowledge-sharing and joint dissemination of research findings	Hosted transformative change sister projects at the final PLANET4B project meeting in Brussels, to exchange insights across projects and identify similarities in research findings through a panel discussion.	11.10.2025
GoDigiBios	Knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Presented PLANET4B's research at a webinar hosted by GoDigiBios.	15.10.2025

4 Strategies for future collaborations beyond the lifetime of the PLANET4B project

Identifying synergies and building collaborations with other projects and initiatives has been instrumental in spreading the reach, uptake and impact of PLANET4B's research. Equally important is the continuation of collaborative activities that will support dissemination and uptake of PLANET4B's research beyond the formal lifetime of the project. By maintaining connections with other projects and initiatives and promoting long-term collaboration, PLANET4B can increase the sustainability and legacy of its research results and outputs. This section outlines strategies for maintaining connection and collaboration between PLANET4B with projects and initiatives beyond

the lifetime of the PLANET4B project. It should be acknowledged that for many partner institutions, it can be challenging to maintain collaboration and joint actions after the completion of the project due to funding and other resource-related constraints. However, recognising the importance of ongoing collaboration, dissemination and exploitation activities, the following strategies are proposed to encourage future collaborations between PLANET4B and other projects in ways that are likely to be realistic and feasible for partner institutions.

4.1 Participation of PLANET4B partners in future events

PLANET4B partners may capitalise on opportunities to communicate and disseminate research and outputs from the PLANET4B project by participating in relevant European and international events. This is particularly applicable for events where other synergistic projects and initiatives are present and where there is scope for presenting research alongside other projects, such as research symposiums, conferences, workshops, and policy forums. Attending these kinds of events could provide fertile ground for PLANET4B partners to establish new connections, share project results and identify new project ideas that build on PLANET4B's research and results.

4.2 Involvement of PLANET4B partners in follow-on projects and initiatives

Building on the new partnerships and collaborations that PLANET4B partners have established as a result of implementing the D5.5 Synergies Strategy, there is high scope for PLANET4B partners to participate in follow-on projects that are informed by and build on the research produced in the PLANET4B project. Those projects may bring together partners involved in the PLANET4B project e.g. the DAISY project (DigitAI, technological and Social innovation mixes enabling transformation for biodiversity and equity), as well as bring in new partners who bring fresh ideas, knowledge and expertise that will help to expand and enrich the research conducted in PLANET4B.

4.3 Involvement of PLANET4B partners in knowledge networks

Partners involved in the PLANET4B project may exploit opportunities to cooperate with other projects and initiatives beyond the lifetime of the project by participating in knowledge networks that align with the research themes addressed in the PLANET4B project. This will require PLANET4B partners to remain proactive about identifying relevant knowledge networks and maintaining engagement and cooperation with other projects via these networks. Examples of knowledge networks that are relevant to the PLANET4B project include:

- Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity (European Commission)
- BiodivClim Knowledge Hub (Biodiversa+)
- BioAgora's knowledge exchange network on transformative change
- NetworkNature
- IUCN Behaviour Change Task Force

5 Conclusion

The implementation of the D5.5 Synergies Strategy has been instrumental for extending the reach, visibility, and impact of PLANET4B's research. By systematically identifying and engaging with complementary projects and initiatives, PLANET4B has established a collaborative environment that supports knowledge-sharing, co-production of research messages, and joint dissemination of research findings. These efforts have ensured PLANET4B's insights on behaviour change, plural values, intersectionality and social inclusion, and transformative change for biodiversity reach broader audiences including policy, business, civil society and academia.

PLANET4B has achieved significant progress in fostering cooperation across Horizon Europe projects and beyond, contributing to greater coherence and alignment across the EU's biodiversity research landscape. Through active participation in clustering activities, joint workshop and webinars and knowledge networks, PLANET4B has demonstrated the value of collaboration as a driver of research impact.

Looking ahead, the partnerships and connections established through the Synergies Strategy provide ample opportunity for sustaining PLANET4B's legacy. Continued engagement in knowledge networks, involvement in follow-on initiatives and participation in European and international fora will enable PLANET4B project partners to further amplify messages and ensure long-term uptake of results. While funding and resource constraints can limit post-project collaboration, the strong foundations laid through the D5.5 Synergies Strategy offer a pathway for ongoing collaboration beyond the lifetime of the project.

References

- Kaye, S., Zolyomi, A., Nel, J., Van Dam, R., Hermans, T., Ingram, V. and Dianoux, R. (2023). Action Plan of Transformative Change Clustering. Available at: <https://planet4b.eu/project-documents/action-plan-of-transformative-change-clustering/>
- Kaye, S. & Zolyomi, A. (2023). Synergies Strategy. Report No D5.5 of the Horizon Europe Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Brussels: European Research Executive Agency. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15479949
Available at: <https://planet4b.eu/project-documents/synergies-strategy/>

Statement on data availability

Some data used to generate the task PLANET4B TCBPI database were accessed from two online open access repositories of projects and initiatives. These are [OpenAIRE Explore](#) and [CODRIS](#).

Statement on ethics

The content described in this D5.6 Updated Synergies Strategy has been developed fully based on publicly accessible repositories and there were no ethical considerations. The contact information relating to projects and initiatives in the PLANET4B TCBPI database in Annex I are all taken from open access websites in the public domain.

Annex

Updated PLANET4B transformative change for biodiversity projects and initiatives (TCBPI) database

Abbreviation of the project/initiative	Full title of the project	Project/initiative	PLANET4B partner leading synergies work	Relevant project link	Project contact
ACCESS	Advancing Capacity for Climate and Environment Social Science	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://accessnetwork.uk/	info@accessnetwork.uk
Access to Justice for a Greener Europe	Access to Justice for a Greener Europe	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.clientearth.org/projects/access-to-justice-for-a-greener-europe/#updates	info@justiceandenvironment.org
Accounting for Nature	Accounting for Nature: Agriculture and Mitigation in the Era of Global Climate Change	Project	ESSRG	http://sdg.graduateinstitute.ch/accounting-for-nature-agriculture-and-mitigation-in-the-era-of-global-climate-change-new-snf-grant-for-prof-shaila-seshia-galvin/	shaila.seshia@graduateinstitute.ch
ACCTING	Advancing behavioural Change Through an INclusive Green deal	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://accting.eu/join-the-network/	accting-eu@esf.org
AGILE	AGILE: Providing rapid evidence-based solutions to the needs of environmental policy-makers	initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.agile-initiative.ox.ac.uk/	kate.oconnor@oxfordmartin.ox.ac.uk
Agroecology-TRANSECT	Trans-disciplinary approaches for systemic economic, ecological and climate change transitions	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.agroecology-transect.net/	https://www.agroecology-transect.net/contact-us/
ANBiot	Agriculture, nature and biodiversity in the transition of territorial socio-ecosystem	Project	FiBL	https://scanr.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/project/ANR-19-CE03-0011	laurie.tissiere@univ-tours.fr
Are Religions becoming Green?	Are Religions becoming Green?	Project	FIBL	https://greenreligion.theologie.unibas.ch/de/are-religions-becoming-green/	https://greenreligion.theologie.unibas.ch/de/kontakt/
ARSINOE	Climate resilient regions through systemic solutions and innovations	Project	CG	https://arsinoe-project.eu/	info@arsinoe-project.eu

A-Track	Accelerating TRAnsformation through Capitals Knowledge	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://a-track.info/	https://a-track.info/a-track/contact
BAMBOO	Biodiversity and trade: mitigating the impacts of non-food biomass and global supply chains	Project	RU	https://bamboo-horizon.eu/	https://bamboo-horizon.eu/contact.html
Basic Needs and Intergenerational Climate Justice	Basic Needs and Intergenerational Climate Justice	Project	TEHRA (previously CAC)	https://basicneeds.uni-graz.at/en/the-project/	lukas.meyer@uni-graz.at
BEATLES	Co-creating Behavioural Change Towards Climate Smart Food Systems	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://beatles-project.eu/	info@beatles-project.eu
BESTMAP	Behavioural, Ecological and socio-economic tools for modelling agricultural policy	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bestmap.eu/	g.ziv@leeds.ac.uk
BiNatUr	Bringing Nature Back – biodiversity-friendly nature-based solutions in cities	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bringingnatureback.com/	kati.vierikko@syke.fi
BioAgora	Connecting biodiversity knowledge and decision making	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bioagora.eu/	https://bioagora.eu/contact/
BIOCONSENT	Decision-making Support for Forest Biodiversity Conservation and Restoration Policy and Management in Europe: Trade-offs and Synergies at the Forest-Biodiversity-Climate-Water Nexus	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/biodivrestore/biodivrestore-transnational-cofund-call-2021/decision-making-support-for-forest-biodiversity-conservation-and-restoration-policy-and-management-in-europe-trade-offs-and-synergies-at-the-forest-biodiversity-climate-water-nexus	https://www.era-learn.eu/network-information/networks/biodivrestore/biodivrestore-transnational-cofund-call-2021/decision-making-support-for-forest-biodiversity-conservation-and-restoration-policy-and-management-in-europe-trade-offs-and-synergies-at-the-forest-biodiversity-climate-water-nexus
Biodiversa+	The European Biodiversity Partnership	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biodiversa.eu/	https://www.biodiversa.eu/contact/

BIOFIN	Protecting and Restoring Biodiversity using Mainstream Finance	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biofin.org/	https://www.biofin.org/about-us
BioMonitor4CAP	Advanced biodiversity monitoring for results-based and effective agricultural policy and transformation	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biomonitor4cap.eu/en/	biomonitor4cap@leibniz-lib.de
BioNext	The Biodiversity Nexus – Triggering Transformative Change for Sustainability (BIONEXT)	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.bionext-project.eu/	bionext.project@syke.fi
BIOTraCes	Biosiversity and transformative change for plural and nature-positive societies	Project	RU	https://www.biotrac.es.eu/	rosalie.vandam@wur.nl
BIOTRAILS	Nexus Framework for biodiversity-relevant transformative change	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://biotrailsproject.eu/	https://biotrailsproject.eu/contact-us/
BioValue	Biodiversity value in spatial policy and planning leveraging multi-level and transformative change	Project	NINA	https://biovalue-horizon.eu/	https://biovalue-horizon.eu/contacts/
BEATLES	Co-creating Behavioural Change Towards Climate-Smart Food Systems	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://beatles-project.eu/	info@beatles-project.eu
BLUEPRINT	BLUEPRINT to a Circular Economy	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://projectblueprint.eu/	https://projectblueprint.eu/partners
BridgingVALUES	'Just' Conservation? Bridging values for equitable biodiversity governance	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biodiversity.eu/2023/04/19/bridgingvalues/#:~:text=BridgingVALUES%20aims%20to%20inform%20conservation,turn%20impact%20biodiversity%20and%20ecosystem	unai.pascual@bc3research.org
CAMPAIGNers	Citizens Acting on Mitigation Pathways through Active Implementation of a Goal-setting Network	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.climate-campaigners.com/Global#rewards	https://project.climate-campaigners.com/Contact
CAOP	Climate Adaptation for Older People Living in Vulnerable Urban Areas: Designing a Climate-responsive and community-based methodology	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://citta.fe.up.pt/projects/1-81-caop-climate-adaptation-for-older-people-living-in-vulnerable-urban-areas-designing-a-climate-responsive-and-community-based-methodology	alves@fe.up.pt

CITVAS	CITVAS Sustainable and smart mobility for all	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	Home CIVITAS	support@civitas.eu
CCRI	Circular Cities & Regions Initiative	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	Circular cities and regions initiative (europa.eu)	helpdesk@circularcities-andregions.eu
CLEVER	Creating Leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade	Project	RU	https://clever-project.eu/	Communications Officer: rosa.castaneda@efi.int
Co-creating and applying a theory of change for biodiversity credits	Co-creating and applying a theory of change for biodiversity credits – towards a nature-positive future	Project	UNEP-WCMC	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pcode=NE%2FX016315%2F1	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pcode=NE%2FX016315%2F1
COEVOLVERS	Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.uni-erfurt.de/en/research/researching/research-projects/coevolvers	carsten.herrmann-pillath@uni-erfurt.de
COOP4CBD	Cooperation for the Convention on Biological Diversity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://twitter.com/coop4cbd	https://twitter.com/coop4cbd
C40 Cities	C40 Cities	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	C40 Cities – A global network of mayors taking urgent climate action	Contact us – C40 Cities
DAISY	DigitAI, technological and Social innovation mixes enabling transformation for biodiversity and equity	Project	MLU	https://www.coventry.ac.uk/research/research-directories/projects/2025/daisy-project/	Agnes.zoloymin@greenformatio.net
DECIPHER	Decision-making framework and processes for holistic evaluation of environmental and climate policies	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://globalclimateforum.org/portfolio-item/decipher/	helen.laubenstein@globalclimateforum.org
Digital Disruption and the Future of Conservation	Digital Disruption and the Future of Conservation	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://unearthodox.org/2022/06/digital-disruption-and-the-future-of-conservation/	info@unearthodox.org
DISES	Between maintenance and transformation: a socio-environmental systems framework for restoration decision-making under climate change	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=2108002	jmantz@nsf.gov
Eclipse	Eclipse	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://eclipse.eu/	https://eclipse.eu/contact/

EmpowerUS	Socio-economic Empowerment of coastal communities as users of the sea to ensure sustainable coastal development	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://empowerus-project.eu/	mbj@nforsk.no
Emys-R	A socio-ecological evaluation of wetlands restoration in favour of the European pond turtle Emys reintroduction and associated biodiversity: a pan-European approach	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://emysr.cnrs.fr/	georges@iphc.cnrs.fr
ENFASYS	Encouraging farmers towards sustainable farming systems through policy and business	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.enfasyproject.eu/	https://www.enfasysproject.eu/contact/
EU-China Environment Project	EU-China Environment Project	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.clientearth.org/projects/eu-china-environment-project/#abouttheproject	https://www.clientearth.org/projects/eu-china-environment-project/#abouttheproject
European City Facility (EUCF)	European City Facility	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	EUCF – Home (eucityfacility.eu)	https://fmp.eucityfacility.eu/iss/NewTicket/
European Urban Initiative (EUI)	European Urban Initiative	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	European Urban initiative	Contact us EUI (urban-initiative.eu)
European Green Capital Award	EU Green Capital and Green Leaf Awards	Award	UNEP-WCMC	European Green Capital Award (europa.eu)	info@european greencapital.eu
EVOCLIM	Behavioral-evolutionary analysis of climate policy: Bounded rationality, markets and social interactions	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.uab.cat/doc/EVOCLIM_PROJECT_AND ITS_RESULTS_EN	https://www.ivanvsavin.org/about
FarmBioNet	Farmer-Focused Biodiversity and Agricultural Knowledge Network	Project	FiBL	https://farmbionet.eu/	Saorla.kavanagh@teagasc.ie
FRESH	Farmer acceptable Restoration of Semi-natural Habitat to limit Herbicides	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.biodiversa.eu/2022/10/25/freshh/	david.bohan@inrae.fr
GenDecCCR	Gendering and Decolonising Climate Change Research: Exploring the Waterberg, South Africa	Project	NINA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101023502	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101023502
GENERATE	Gender, Generation and Climate Change: Creative Approaches to Building Inclusive and Climate Resilient Cities in Uganda and Myanmar	Project	FUG	https://gtr.ukri.org/projects?ref=MR%2FS015299%2F1	https://gtr.ukri.org/person/EECFB85C-8835-4446-A089-B5E71DA0F278

Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (GCoM)	Data4Cities, Innovate4Cities, and Invest4Cities	Covenant with Initiatives	UNEP-WCMC	Our Initiatives new – Global Covenant of Mayors	info@globalcovenantofmayors.org
GoDigiBioS	Biodiversity loss mitigation and adaptation measures: Policies Governance and tools to foster transformative change	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.godigibios.eu/#/	marcos.nogueira@isg.pt
Green City Accord	Green City Accord	Platform/ Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	Green City Accord (europa.eu)	contact@greencityaccord.eu
Green Talent	Building Capacity and Partnerships for Systemic Solutions to the Climate and Biodiversity Crisis	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://bsky.app/profile/green-talent.bsky.social	https://www.linkedin.com/company/green-talent-project/
GrowGreen	GrowGreen Project	Project	UNEP-WCMC	Home – GrowGreen (growgreenproject.eu)	Contact – GrowGreen (growgreenproject.eu)
GUARDEN	SafeGUARDing biodiversity and critical ecosystem services across sectors and scales	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://guarden.org/	https://guarden.org/contact-us/
HABITABLE	Linking Climate Change, Habitability and Social Tipping Points: Scenarios for Climate Migration	Project	FiBL	https://habitableproject.org/	https://habitableproject.org/contact/
HEICCAM	The health and equity impact of climate change mitigation measures on indoor and outdoor air pollution exposure	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://heiccam.org/#:~:text=HEICCAM%20(Health%20and%20Equity%20Impacts,to%20a%20low%20carbon%20future.	info@heiccam.org
INCENTIVE	Establishing Citizen Science Hubs in European Research Performing and Funding Organisations to drive institutional change and ground Responsible Research and Innovation in society	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://incentive-project.eu/about/incentive-goals/	info@incentive-project.eu
INNATURE	Enhancing biodiversity and social inclusion by transforming Europe's living environments	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://innature-project.eu/	https://innature-project.eu/contact-us/
Interlace	International cooperation to restore and connect urban environments in Latin America and Europe	Project	FUG	https://www.interlace-project.eu/	https://www.interlace-project.eu/contact

IUCN Behaviour Change Task Force	IUCN Behaviour Change Task Force	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.conservationbehaviourchange.org/	https://www.conservationbehaviourchange.org/contact
IPCJ	The International People's Platform for Climate Justice	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://ourclimateimpact.org/	https://ourclimateimpact.org/contact-us/
JustFutures	Climate Futures and Just Transformations: Young People's Narratives and Political Imaginaries	Project	TEHRA (previously CAC)	https://justfutures.pt/en/home-en/	carlamalafaia@fpce.up.pt
Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity	Knowledge Centre for biodiversity of the European Commission	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/biodiversity_en	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/biodiversity/about_en
Knowledge4Policy	Knowledge4Policy	Platform	UNEP-WCMC	Knowledge for policy (europa.eu)	Give us feedback Knowledge for policy (europa.eu)
Local Nature Innovation Fund	Local Nature Innovation Fund	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://experiments.friendsoftheearth.uk/projects/local-nature-innovation-fund-supporting-nature-projects-grassroots	https://r1.dotdigital-pages.com/p/78W4-6J3/contact-experiments-team?origin=is1
Mapping for good	Mapping for good	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.kartevonmorgen.org/en	https://blog.vonmorgen.org/en/contact/
MOCHA	Understanding and leveraging 'moments of change' for pro-environmental behaviour shifts	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.cardiff.ac.uk/psychology/research/impact/moments-of-change-mocha	whitmarshle@cardiff.ac.uk
MOSAIC	Joined-up land use strategies tackling climate change and biodiversity loss	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.vlaanderen.be/inbo/en-GB/projects/mosaic-evinbo	Julie.callebaut@inbo.be
NaturaConnect	Designing a Resilient and Coherent Trans-European Network for Nature and People	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://naturaconnect.eu/	naturaconnect@iiasa.ac.at
Naturescapes	Nature-based solutions for climate resilient, nature positive and socially just communities in diverse landscapes	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.naturescapes-project.com/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/naturescapes30
NATURVATION	NATURVATION	Project	UNEP-WCMC	NATURVATION 	(18) Dora Almassy LinkedIn

Net Zero	Net Zero Climate	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://netzeroclim.org/	https://netzeroclim.org/contact-us/
Network Nature	Network Nature	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://networknature.eu/	https://networknature.eu/helpdesk
Oppla	Oppla	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://oppla.eu/	https://oppla.eu/contacts
PASTOPRAXIS	Local adaptative responses of pastoralism to climate change in the Natural Park of Montesinho Portugal	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://pastopraxis.cimo.ipb.pt/pastopraxis/web/index.php?r=site%2Findex&language=pt#inicio	marina.castro@ipb.pt
Pathways2Resilience	Pathways 2 Resilience	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.pathways2resilience.eu/	hello@pathways2resilience.eu
People, rice and mangroves at the margins	People, rice and mangroves at the margins: A hybrid and contested interface in a changing world	Project	RU	https://www.ces.uc.pt/en/investigacao/projetos-de-investigacao/projetos-financiados/margins	https://www.ces.uc.pt/en/investigacao/projetos-de-investigacao/projetos-financiados/margins
PLAN'EAT	PLAN'EAT	Project	FIBL	https://planeat-project.eu/	https://planeat-project.eu/contact/
PLUS change	Planning land use strategies: meeting biodiversity, climate and social objectives in a changing world	Project	CG	https://www.czechglobe.cz/en/projects/?project=PLUS&provider=0&year_from=&year_to=	CG partners
Pro-climate	Proactive community adaptation to climate change through social transformation	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://pro-climate.eu/	https://pro-climate.eu/
PRUDENT	Promoting Green Nudging for Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://prudent-project.eu/	info@prudent-project.eu
Rainforest	Co-produced transformative knowledge to accelerate change for biodiversity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://rainforest-horizon.eu/index.html	https://rainforest-horizon.eu/contact.html
REDESIGN	Transformative food Systems reshaping resilient urban landscapes	Project	IFZ	https://distal.unibo.it/en/news/redesign-the-horizon-europe-project-will-be-co-coordinated-by-michele-d-ostuni-and-francesco-orcin	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101182261

RELATE	Environmental Spaces and the Feel-Good Factor: Relating Subjective Wellbeing to Biodiversity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/726104	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/726104
RESPIN	REinforce Science-Policy interfaces in innovative ways to boost effectiveness and INTERconnectedness of biodiversity and climate policies	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://respin-project.eu/	contact@respin-project.eu
RURALIZATION	The opening of rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://ruralization.eu/	https://ruralization.eu/contact/
SCALAR	Scaling up behavior and autonomous adaptation for macro models of climate change damage assessment	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://europepmc.org/grantfinder/grantdetails?query=pi%3A%22Filatova%20T%22%20gid%3A%22758014%22%20ga%3A%22European%20Research%20Council%22	T.Filatova@utwente.nl
SELINA	Science for Evidence-Based and Sustainable Decisions about Natural Capital	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://project-selina.eu/	burkhard@phygeo.uni-hannover.de
Shared Green Deal	Shared Green Deal	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://sharedgreendeal.eu/	chris.foulds@aru.ac.uk rosie.robison@aru.ac.uk
SSH CENTRE	Social Sciences and Humanities for Climate, Energy and Transport Research Excellence	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://sshcentre.eu/	chris.foulds@aru.ac.uk rosie.robison@aru.ac.uk
StartClim	StartClim	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://startclim.at/startseite	https://startclim.at/kontakt
SUSTAIN	Strengthening Understanding and Strategies of business to Assess and Integrate Nature	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://capitalscoalition.org/project/sustain-project/	info@capitalscoalition.org
Sustainable Healthy Cities	Sustainable Healthy Cities Network for Integrated Urban Infrastructure Solutions	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	Sustainable Healthy Cities Network	yingling@umn.edu
TC4BE	Transformative Change in Telecoupled Agrofood Systems for Biodiversity and Equity	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082057	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082057
The Concept of Vulnerability in the Context of Human Rights	The Concept of Vulnerability in the Context of Human Rights	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://gmr.lbg.ac.at/projects/project-the-concept-of-vulnerability-in-the-context-of-	monika.mayrhofer@gmr.lbg.ac.at

				human-rights/?lang=en	
The Future of Conservation NGOs	The Future of Conservation NGOs	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://unearthodox.org/2022/12/future-of-conservation-ngos/	info@unearthodox.org
TIME4CS	Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.time4cs.eu/about	time4cs@apre.it
Together for 1.5	Together for 1.5: Accelerate Climate Action in Europe	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://1point5.caneurope.org/	https://1point5.caneurope.org/contact/
TOWCHED	Transforming Our World: Collections at the Heart of life-long learning and Education	Project	TEHRA (previously CAC)	https://towched.eu/	info@towched.eu
TRANSCLIM	Transformative Transparency? Assessing the Effects of Reporting and Review in the International Climate Change Regime	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://sites.uef.fi/cceel/transclim/	https://sites.uef.fi/cceel/transclim/
Transition Network	Transition Network	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	About the Movement – Transition Network Movement of Communities	Transition Network Contact Us
Transformations Community	Transformations Community	Initiative	CG	https://www.transformationscommunity.org/	https://www.transformationscommunity.org/contact-us
Transformative Pathways	Transformative Pathways	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.forestpeoples.org/en/transformative-pathways#:~:text=Transformative%20Pathways%20is%20a%20joint%20initiative%20led%20by,recognising%20C%20supporting%20and%20expanding%20contributions%20by%20indigenous%20peoples.	https://www.forestpeoples.org/en/contact
TRANS-lighthouses	More than green – Lighthouses of transformative nature-based solutions for inclusive communities	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://portal.research.lu.se/sv/projects/more-than-green-lighthouses-of-transformative-nature-based-soluti	ana.mm.arroz@uac.pt

Transpath	Transformative pathways for synergising just biodiversity and climate actions	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.ufz.de/index.php?en=50052	Sindy Bleiholder sekces@ufz.de Phone: +49 341 235-1250
UNEP GEO 7	UNEP Global Environment Outlook 7 – working group on “social justice and behaviour change”	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.unep.org/geo/global-environment-outlook-7	https://www.unep.org/geo/global-environment-outlook-7
UNPplus	Enhanced Urban Nature Plans for Biodiversity Mainstreaming in Society	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://urbannatureplans.eu/documents/ugpplus-enhanced-urban-greening-plans-biodiversity-mainstreaming-society	hello@urbannatureplans.eu
Upsurge	Upsurge Project	Project	UNEP-WCMC	UPSURGE Project – The European Union Regenerative Urban Lighthouse Project (upsurgeproject.eu)	info@upsurgeproject.eu
URBAN GreenUP	URBAN GreenUP	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.urban-greenup.eu/	rausan@cartif.es
URBACT	URBACT	Initiative	UNEP-WCMC	Who we are urbact.eu	communication@urbact.eu
ValMaB – DM	Valuing Marine Biodiversity for use in Decision Making	Project	UNEP-WCMC	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pcode=NE%2FX002357%2F1	http://gotw.nerc.ac.uk/list_full.asp?pcode=NE%2FX002357%2F1
ValueChange	Design for changing values: a theory of value change in sociotechnical systems	Project	NINA	https://www.valuechange.eu/	info@valuechange.eu
Wageningen Biodiversity Initiative	Wageningen Biodiversity Initiative	Initiative	MLU	https://www.wur.nl/en/themes/biodiversity/what-is-the-wageningen-biodiversity-initiative.html	biodiversity@wur.nl
wildE	Climate-smart rewilding: ecological restoration for climate change mitigation, adaptation and biodiversity support in Europe	Project	UNEP-WCMC	https://www.wilde-project.eu/	https://www.wilde-project.eu/contact
WOW	The Writing's on the Wall	Project	TEHRA (previously CAC)	https://thewritingsonthewall.org/	hello@thewritingsonthewall.org